

Real, Foley or synthetic? An evaluation of everyday walking sounds

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to evaluate whether foley sounds, real recordings and low quality synthetic sounds can be distinguished when used to sonify a video and if foley sounds can be rated as more expressive than real sounds. The main idea is to find a motivation for having such a solid tradition in using foley sounds for a film track. In particular this work focuses on walking sounds: five different scenes of a walking person were video recorded and each video was then mixed with the three different kind of sounds mentioned above. Subjects were asked to recognise and describe the action performed, to evaluate their confidence, the realism of the action and its expressiveness. Early results shows that foley sounds and real sounds cannot be distinguished by the subjects. A preliminary audio-only test was performed with the sounds used in the audio-video test in order to assess the recognition rate without the visual help.

1. INTRODUCTION

While existing for several decades, Foley sound effects (cf. [1]) are still an elusive research topic. They are widely used in the movie and video industries because the direct location recordings of scene sounds are simply not good enough or plagued anyway with all sorts of noises that are bound to appear on a crowded set, but their techniques of production are still considered an art which defies explanation (cf. [1,2]). In general, Foley artists learn by experience and know what to do in every particular situation they have to represent, but they hardly know *why* the sounds they produce work well in a given context – being often far more expressive than the direct recording materials. Furthermore, scientific literature about Foley effects is quite scarce (cf. [3–5]) and a wide area of investigation, ranging from multi-modal perception to audio feature evaluation, is available to researchers. However, several experimental studies can be found on the identification and classification of environmental sounds [6], for instance comparing different kind of synthesis [7], introducing the concept of *types of similarities* that can be used as a strategy in a classification task [8,9], or analysing in depth the lexicon that

is used for different environmental sound categories [10]. In [11] the authors claim that according to listener expertise and their confidence scores the similarity approach that they used can be predicted quite well: expert participants usually refer to acoustical similarities, while non experts refer to causal similarities. Following the results of the mentioned work, we decided to ask our *non expert* subjects to identify the action performed, implicitly suggesting to find a causal similarity to identify the sounds they had to judge.

The sounds of walking over different surfaces and materials occupy a special place within the domain of everyday sounds (or environmental sounds) present in video sequences. This everyday life task is really quite complex to reproduce faithfully in a virtualized environment (cf. [12,13]) but its ubiquity constitutes an indispensable know-how in the idiomatic repertoire of any professional foley artist. Thus, in this experiment walking sounds were considered the most fitted to investigate the current status of sound perception in a direct confrontation between foley, real and synthetic sounds.

The main purpose of this investigation is to compare user recognition and appreciation of footstep sounds in an AV production context. The starting idea was to assert the recognition capabilities and their precision first with audio-only stimuli and then with audio-video ones. In order to do that, an experiment was conducted by asking subjects to express preference and confidence ratings over a group of stimuli presented both in audio-only and audio-video forms. The subjects were also asked to describe the action generating the sounds they were hearing and complete freedom was left to them for the description. A large majority of subjects ended up describing both an action *and* the supposed material over which it was performed. A very crude early semantic analysis was then applied to the descriptions of the audio-only sounds in an attempt to discern whether the subjects were actually recognizing actions and materials at all or whether they were recognizing appropriately one or the other.

2. METHOD

To achieve the goal stated in the last paragraph of Sec.1, we recorded footstep sounds on several surfaces, and we also reproduced their Foley counterpart, using techniques adopted from the movie industry. Moreover, we re-synthesized a low-quality version of the original sounds to be used as a control condition in the assessment of sound quality.

Figure 1. Recording footsteps on sand by massaging and squeezing a little bag filled with salt.

2.1 Visual stimuli

The videos were recorded with a Canon 7D camera. They all last about 20 second and they represent 5 different scenes: a man walking on a wooden pavement, a men walking outside on concrete, a men walking outside on sand, a men walking outside on gravel, a men walking outside on grass.

2.2 Auditory stimuli

2.2.1 Foley sounds

All audio recordings were performed inside the anechoic chamber at AAU Copenhagen, Multisensory experiences lab. The "foley artist" was not a professional one, but a well documented PHd student, that used the same acknowledge techniques and the same professional equipment that is usually used in a foley recording studio. On the floor in the anechoic chamber a platform consisting of two large wooden boards with slices wall-to-wall carpeting in between was placed. The platform was resting on six legs that were fixed below the wire floor. Footsteps were produced with a walking-in-place-like treading. A Neuman U87 microphone was used for the recording, connected to an RME Fireface 800 audio interface.

- **Footsteps on Sand:**
Salt was put into a shoe bag made of thin fabric. The final footstep sounds consisted of two recordings: one where the bag with salt was patted in a waving motion. This was to emulate the impact of the foot. The other recording was with the bag being held in one hand while being moved in circular patterns with the other hand. This was to emulate the sand being moved around by the foot. See fig. 1
- **Footsteps on Gravel:**
A Foley pit created with a wooden box (16mm MDF boards, dimensions 60, 100, 15 cm) was built. The insides were covered with polystyrene material to help dampening the wooden resonance of the wooden construction. A thick felt blanket was also added on top of the polystyrene. The box was filled with approximately 25 Liters of gravel (8-16 mm stones).

Figure 2. Recording footsteps on wood by walking in place.

- **Footsteps on Concrete:** A concrete slab was placed into the Foley pit filled with gravel (described above).
- **Footsteps on Wood:** A wooden pallet was placed on the platform. Thick felt blankets were stuffed under the boards of the pallet to alter the resonance of the pallet, see fig. 2
- **Wooden creaks:** Creaks were recorded by using a partially broken wooden pallet. The wooden creaks were added to the recordings of footsteps by manual editing during postproduction.
- **Footsteps on grass:** Tape from a VHS cassette was placed on the platform and patted on with waving strokes to emulate the walking on grass.

2.2.2 Real sounds

The following real recordings were chosen because they were recorded on actual locations (but different from where the videos were recorded) and not Foley:

- Grass sounds were taken from Freesound.org user Zoom H4 ;
- Gravel sounds were taken from user Spleencast ;
- Sand was taken from user DasDeer;
- Concrete was taken from user conleec
- Wooden floor was taken from user sinatra314.

2.2.3 Environmental sounds

To compensate the cleanliness of the foley sounds (recorded in anechoic conditions) and of the synthesized sounds versus the real sound samples, a fake background was added to them. The purpose was to avoid accidental recognition of the foley/synthesized sounds related to the difference in noise content between audio samples.

The two environment sounds used in the experiment were recorded with a Zoom H4n recorder. One recording is of an outdoor environment with distant traffic noises, the other recording was made inside an apartment living room.

The editing and synchronizing of the all the footstep sounds to the videos were done in Adobe Audition CS6. The editing of the Foley recordings were done as would have been normally edited in a film mix with post-production applied where it was deemed necessary.

2.2.4 Synthesized sounds

In order to assess whether subjects rated a lower quality reproduction of the recorded sounds with a lower mark, a set of synthetic footstep sounds was created. The sounds were created as follows. First of all the amplitude envelope of the original recordings (real sounds) was extracted, by using the following simple non-linear low-pass filter proposed by Cook ([14]):

$$e(n) = (1 - b(n))|x(n)| + b(n)e(n - 1)$$

where

$$b = \begin{cases} b_{up} & \text{if } |x(n)| > e(n - 1) \\ b_{down} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

with $b_{up} = 0.8$ and $b_{down} = 0.995$.

The original sounds were also passed through a 48th order LPC filter, in order to estimate the main resonances.

The synthetic sounds were obtained by using white noise as input, which became filtered through the LPC filter and with the amplitude obtained by multiplying sample-wise the original amplitude to the values of the estimated amplitude envelope.

The resulting synthetic footsteps present a similar amplitude evolution of the original ones, but the content is significantly noisier given the input signal used for the LPC filter. This can be easily perceived in the simulated footsteps on solid surfaces such as wood, where the sharp attack obtained in the original sounds is lost in the synthesis.

2.3 Testing interface and procedure

The same testing interface has been used for both the audio-video test and the preliminary audio only one. It was created using Max/MSP: subjects could see the video (or a black window in the audio test) and listen to the sound, make their evaluation on the same window and switch to the next trial when done, see fig. 3. The order of presentation of the stimuli (both audio and audio-video) was randomized for each participant. They were asked to describe the action that they were looking/listening to, to rate how confident they were with their identification, how realistic and how expressive was the scene in the likert scale from 1 to 5. No further explanation were given to them, letting them free to describe as much (or as little) as they wanted. We wanted to investigate how much they were going to describe the scene in the two different tests: will they focus on the action or also something else, like the materials involved, the environment, the speed walking etc.). There were 16 subjects (7 female and 9 male) who participated to the preliminary audio test. The mean age was 27 years, and the range was 21 to 42 years. All participants reported normal hearing and either normal or corrected-to-normal vision. All the participants completed the test. The same

Figure 3. The Max/MSP patch dispensed to the subjects for evaluation of video and audio.

16 subjects plus other 14, for a total of 30 subjects (10 female and 20 male) participated to the audio-video test. The mean age for this test was 28 and the range was from 21 to 46 years old. The test lasted around 20 minutes for each condition.

The test was performed using a HP ProBook 6460b with a 14 inch screen along with the RME Fireface 800 and Sennheiser 600HD. The videos were presented at a resolution of 960*540 pixels.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

The audio and audio-video tests produced two very dissimilar overall results: the audio-video tests featured of course a solid recognition both in terms of actions and materials, while in the audio-only test recognition was much more of an issue. Therefore, we decided to supplement the analysis of the audio tests with an evaluation of the quality of the recognition through the textual description proposed by the subjects.

3.1 Audio test

In order to qualify appropriately the evaluation given by subjects about the sound stimuli that were dispensed to them, it was necessary to discern the extent to which the subjects themselves had recognized the action and/or the material present within each stimulus. The audio-only test shows some preliminary and qualitative results concerning this aspect: most of the subjects could not identify correctly the action performed *both* the action (walking) *and* the material (concrete, gravel, grass, sand, wood), but we found out that many of them could identify just one of the two aspects.

Since the subjects were left completely free to describe what they were hearing both in terms of the action performed and in terms of the materials on/over/with which the action was performed, we then re-processed all free-form answers attributing to them two different scores, one concerning the action and one concerning the recognition of the material.

Given the preliminary status of this work and the (small) amount of data collected, we did not perform a fully detailed statistical analysis of the results (such as that found, for example, in [11]). However, we are fully aware that

Figure 4. Correctness of the answers of the participants concerning actions.

such an analysis is to be carried out on a more definitive statement on this subject.

The scores were attributed on a scale from 0 to 2 in the following way:

- 0 was attributed to the text when the subject expressed the impossibility of discerning anything out of the stimulus proposed (i.e. phrases like “I don’t know” or “...” or “I cannot figure it out” etc.)
- 1 was attributed to the text description when the subject was actually able to provide an explanation as to what kind of action was being performed and what kind of material was being used, but the explanation was clearly wrong (i.e. the subject did not recognize either the action and/or the material)
- 2 was attributed to the text description when the subject was actually able to provide an explanation as to what kind of action was being performed and what kind of material was being used, and the explanation was correct to some extent (i.e. the subject provided a description that was amenable to let us understand that she/he indeed *did* recognize the action and/or the material used in the given stimulus)

The rationale behind this scoring system is that in this case a wrong answer is better than no answer at all, and this is reflected in the way grades are applied to each text description.

Fig.4 and 5 show quite distinctly some specific features of these results:

- a) in general, actions (cf. fig.4) are better recognized than materials (cf. fig.5);
- b) the stimulus “walking on wood” (columns 13, 14 and 15) is distinctly the better recognized one both in terms of action and of material by most subjects, at least as far as foley and real sound actions are concerned
- c) the stimuli “waking on concrete” (columns 1 – 3) and “walking on gravel” (columns 4 – 6) come next in terms of recognition
- d) the stimuli “walking on grass” (columns 7 – 9) and “waking on sand” (columns 10 – 13) give the worst

Figure 5. Correctness of the answers of the participants concerning materials.

results in terms of recognition; the difficulty comes mostly from the recognition of the material, but this very often jeopardizes the recognition of the action too

e) the recognition of synthetic sound probes (columns 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15) is much more difficult and unstable

An early conjecture regarding these results is that there seems to be some correlation between the quantity of acoustic resonance present in a stimulus and the capability of recognition: more resonating materials (wood, concrete, gravel) stand a larger chance of being recognized than less resonating ones. However, this conjecture has not been investigated further at this time as it has been left for future research.

3.2 Audio-Video test

The audio-video test was analysed starting from the media and its variance. The variance was found to be too large to further proceed with anova tests over it. The median values were then evaluated and the Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney test performed. Figures 6, 7, 8 shows the median values for each trial:

1. Walking on concrete with foley sounds, real and synthesized sounds
2. Walking on gravel with foley sounds, real and synthesized sounds
3. Walking on grass with foley sounds, real and synthesized sounds
4. Walking on sand with foley sounds, real and synthesized sounds
5. Walking on wood with foley sounds, real and synthesized sounds

A preliminary observation of the data already shows some interesting results:

- given the video of the action the confidence 6 of the subject on their answers were quite high showing always better confidence on videos with foley and real sounds then on synthesised sounds.
- this trend is even more evident looking in figures n. 7

and 8 where both the expressiveness and the realism of the action are rated higher for the first two kinds of sounds.

- the realism of the videos on walking on sand and on grass where rated lower than the others (gravel, concrete and wood).
- the expressiveness of the video with gravel sounds as feedback is the highest

Figure 6. Median values of the confidence ratings for each trial

Figure 7. Median values of the realism ratings for each trial

4. DISCUSSION

The Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney test was performed to test the null hypothesis that data of two trials are samples from continuous distributions with equal medians, against the alternative that they are not. For each material (concrete, gravel, grass, sand, wood) the p value has been computed between the 3 possible combination of the sound feedback: foley and real, foley and synthetic, real and synthetic. For the confidence rate it was always possible to confirm the null hypothesis, giving the analysis always high p values, while the analysis was slightly more interesting for the evaluation of the action realism and expressiveness. It was

Figure 8. Median values of the expressiveness ratings for each trial

always possible to reject the null hypothesis comparing real or foley sounds with the synthetic ones, showing that even with the video, subjects could recognise the poor audio feedback, while subjects could not really distinguish between real and foley sounds. This was true both for the actions that got quite high median values and for the actions that got bad evaluation in terms of the median value (in particular sand and grass). It is interesting to notice that walking on gravel and walking on wood were the two actions with the higher expressiveness median value: the same behaviour can be noticed in the evaluation of the realism of the scene, showing a correlation between the two aspects.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work is a preliminary study on foley walking sounds. The analysis of the data shows that recognizing the walking action by just listening to the sounds is a really difficult task. Very few subjects could recognise both the action and the material upon which the action was performed, without any significant difference between real and foley sounds. The same result was achieved in the audio-video test: in this case the action was recognised for all trials, but realism and expressiveness of the action were dramatically dependent on the sound feedback used and on the material used for the walking surface. Subjects could recognise the synthetic sounds and expressed their preferences for real/foley sounds; walking on sand and walking on grass were the two lowest rated actions as they were the hardest to recognize. This aspect is particularly interesting because these two actions were performed in some awkward way as foley, using other materials-gestures to mimic the sound of a walking gesture. That was the way they are usually performed when foleys of such sounds are required. So, the original idea was that for some reason these sounds should be more expressive, since that is the way these foleys are usually performed. But this was not the case. Further investigation should be carried out in order to analyze why some materials-gestures work better than others and what kind of information about the walker or the walking gesture can be conveyed using the different surfaces.

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